

Table 5.1: Comparison of the scope of data protection legislation.

Theme	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Personal Scope	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; Emphasis on data protection; Children cannot consent	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; Focus on data protection (wide scope); Children cannot consent	<i>Opt-out</i> consent; Emphasis on corporate freedom; Children can consent from the age of 13	<i>Opt-in</i> consent; Focus on data protection (less comprehensive); No minimum age for consent	<i>Opt-out</i> consent; Emphasis on corporate freedom; Children can consent from the age of 13
Territorial Scope	Applies to organizations in Brazil or abroad, as long as they process Brazilian data	It applies to organizations in EU or outside, as long as it processes European data	Applies only to the processing of data of individuals residing in the United States.	Applies to APP entities (organizations) that may or may not be in Australia	It applies to any for-profit entity doing business in California
Material Scope	Sensitive personal data (direct association); Comprises personal data of employees	Sensitive personal data (direct and indirect association); Includes personal data of employees	Sensitive personal data; does not include personal data of employees	Sensitive personal data; Comprises personal data of employees; Comprises opinion as personal data	Sensitive personal data; does not include personal data of employees

Table 5.2: Comparison of data protection legislation definitions.

Theme	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Responsible for Treatment	Controller, operator and en-loaded	Controller, processor and DPO	Covered entities and service providers	APP Entities	Businesses and service providers
Personal data	Information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person	Information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person	Covered Data (identifiable data of a natural person)	Any information about an individual held by a federal agency	Information that identifies, describes or can be associated with a consumer or their family
Sensitive data	Any information relating to an identified or identifiable person	Any information relating to an identified or identifiable person	Sensitive Covered Data (special categories of personal data)	Any information about an individual held by a federal agency	Information that identifies, describes or can be associated with a consumer or their family
Data processor	Operator (entity that processes personal data on behalf of the controller)	Processor (natural or legal person who carries out the data processing on behalf of the controller)	Service provider (service provider that processes data for a contracted entity)	Not applicable (the focus is on federal agencies as controllers)	Service provider (entity that processes personal information on behalf of a business)

Table 5.3: Comparison of administrative sanctions in data protection legislation.

Theme	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Sanctions	Up to 2% of turnover excluding taxes (limited to 50 million reais) or daily fine according to total limit	Up to 20 million euros or 4% of total turnover for the previous fiscal year for more serious violations, reduced to up to 10 million euros or 2% of turnover for minor violations	No specifically defined administrative fines, but organizations that violate the ADPPA may still be subject to government enforcement actions and private rights of action	For serious and repeated interference up to \$2,500,000 for individuals and up to \$50,000,000 for legal entities, or three times the benefit obtained, or 30% of adjusted turnover	From \$2,500 to \$7,500 per violation and statutory damages between \$100 and \$750, offering a 30-day period for correction.

Table 5.4: Comparison of the definitions of the data protection principles.

Principles	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Purpose	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44]	✓ Y/S [44]
Suitability	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44]	✓ Y/S [44]
Need	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44],[49]	✓ Y/S [44]
Free Access	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/C	✓ Y/S [44],[49]	✓ Y/D
Data Quality	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44],[49]	N/A
Transparency	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44],[49]	✓ Y/S [44]
Security	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44]	✓ Y/S [44]
Prevention	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/O	N/A
Non-discrimination	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/D	N/A	✓ Y/S [44]
Accountability	✓ Y/S [36],[43],[7]	✓ Y/S [36],[43]	✓ Y/C	N/A	✓ Y/S [44]

Table 5.5: Comparison of the definitions of data protection rights.

Rights	LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Minimized collection	✓ Y/S [43]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [45]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/C
Confirmation of Existence of Treatment	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [36]	N/A	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44],[46]
Data Access	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [44],[46]
Data correction	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/S [44],[49]	✓ Y/O
Anonymization	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/C	N/A	✓ Y/D	N/A
Data portability	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [45]	N/A	✓ Y/S [44],[46]
Data deletion	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/O	N/A	✓ Y/S [44],[46]
Information on Participating Entities	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/O
Information on the Possibility of Not Consenting	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/C	N/A	✓ Y/O
Revocation of Consent	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/S [44]	✓ Y/S [44]
Challenge	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/S [36]	✓ Y/O	N/A	✓ Y/S [44]
Processing Consistent with Purpose	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [45]	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/O
Retention Consistent with Finality	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/D	✓ Y/S [45]	✓ Y/D	N/A
Opposition to Automated Decision-Making	✓ Y/O	✓ Y/S [36]	N/A	N/A	N/A
Processing Restriction	✓ Y/C	✓ Y/S [36]	N/A	N/A	✓ Y/O